

English Recruitment Message

Participant Recruitment: Casino Gamblers with Experience in Land-Based Casinos

We are a research team from *****, and we are recruiting participants for an academic interview study on gamblers' safety experiences in modern land-based casinos equipped with digital devices.

This study focuses on legally operated physical casinos that incorporate digital devices into the gambling environment. We aim to better understand how gamblers experience safety, risk, and control in modern casino settings, especially when interacting with digital devices and systems.

Who can participate?

You may be eligible if you meet all of the following criteria:

- You can speak English
- You are 18 years old or above
- You have visited a legally operated physical (offline) casino
- You have placed at least one bet in an offline casino
- You have interacted with digital or electronic devices or systems in a casino,

such as:

- slot machines or electronic gaming machines
- digital table games or electronic betting terminals
- player loyalty or membership systems
- digital payment, ticket-in/ticket-out, or account-based systems

What will participation involve?

- A one-on-one online interview
- Conducted via Zoom or a similar online meeting platform
- Approximately 45 – 60 minutes

Participants will receive reasonable compensation for their time.

If you are interested, please feel free to contact me.

[Where permitted by platform rules and restrictions, the posted recruitment message also included a sign-up link.]

Chinese Recruitment Message

受访者招募: 具有线下赌场经历的赌客

我们是来自 ***** 的研究团队, 现正在招募受访者参与一项学术访谈研究, 主题聚焦于赌客在现代赌场环境 (特质当前那些配备数字设备的赌场环境) 中的安全体验。

我们希望进一步了解, 赌客在与这些数字设备和系统互动时, 如何感知自身的安全、风险与控制感。

招募对象

如果您符合以下全部条件, 则可能适合参与本研究:

- 年满 18 周岁
- 曾进入过合法运营的线下赌场
- 曾在线下赌场中至少实际下注过一次
- 曾在线下赌场中接触或使用过数字或电子设备/系统, 例如:
 - 老虎机或电子博彩机
 - 数字桌面博彩设备或电子下注终端
 - 会员/积分系统
 - 数字支付、票券进出票券系统或账户制系统

参与方式

- 一对一线上访谈
- 通过 Zoom 或腾讯会议平台进行语音对话
- 时长约 45 – 60 分钟

参与者将获得合理报酬以感谢您付出的时间。

如果您有兴趣参与, 请私信与我联系, 或扫描下方二维码报名。